

ANALYSIS PLAN

Title: Speed-Incentivized Reward Learning Task
Abbreviation: SPIRL
Date: 04 April 2022
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1 FOREWORD

This document contains the analysis plan of the project entitled “Speed-Incentivized Reward Learning Task” (SPIRL).

The project concerns the analysis of behavioural data (binary predictions and continuous-valued response times) from a healthy volunteer study on speed-incentivized reward learning that is being conducted at the Translational Neuromodeling Unit (TNU). The pilot data set comprises data of 20 healthy volunteers and the main data set contains data of 60 healthy volunteers.

The purpose of this analysis plan is to provide a brief background for the proposed work, formulate the research question(s), explicitly describe planned and potential post-hoc analyses, and give the rationale for each analysis step. All code created over the course of this study will be version-controlled and documented on the internal GITLab (<https://tnurepository.ethz.ch>) of the TNU.

A side note regarding the temporal evolution of this analysis plan: The very last section (REVISIONS) of this document contains a dated list of changes and additions made throughout the entire process. Importantly,

- version 1 (date effective: 14.04.2021): contains all analysis steps up to (and including) the analysis of the pilot data set (section 8).
- version 2 (date effective: 04.04.2022): analysis of the main data set (section 9) added, which are based on the results from analysing the pilot data. Note that up to this point, the parts of the analysis involving only the pilot data and/or synthetic data generated by our models have already been conducted (sections 9.2.2 - 9.2.3), which was necessary in order to be able to finalize the model space required for hypothesis testing. To emphasise the distinction between parts of the analysis that have yet to be conducted versus those that have already been conducted upon publication of version 2 of this analysis plan, different tenses are used to describe the respective parts (i.e. past tense for analyses that have already been conducted up to this point and future tense for analyses that will be conducted after publication of version 2 of this analysis plan).

Remark: The empirical data from the main data set remain untouched and will only be analysed after publication of version 2 of the analysis plan.

2 INTRODUCTION

Computational models of behaviour provide useful insights about the formation and updating of beliefs and how these translate into behaviour. The Hierarchical Gaussian Filter (HGF)(Mathys et al., 2011, 2014) is a generic hierarchical Bayesian framework for individual learning under multiple forms of uncertainty formulated in the "observing the observer"

framework (Daunizeau et al., 2010b, 2010a). The HGF represents a possible implementation of Bayesian belief updating that rests on simple one-step update equations allowing for online learning. Critically, and in contrast to many other models that have emerged from Bayesian Brain theories such as Predictive Coding models (Friston, 2005; Rao and Ballard, 1999), the HGF can be fit to empirical data when combined with an appropriate response model. These response or observation models specify a mapping from hidden states (beliefs) to observable actions (measured responses). Inference on hidden belief states and parameter values, characterizing an individual's behaviour, enables the quantification of individual behaviour. This is particularly useful for the young field of Computational Psychiatry, yielding a potential tool for systematic investigation of maladaptive behaviour.

However, a crucial factor in this endeavour is the reliability and robustness of statistical inference. The amount of information contained in empirical data is of fundamental importance for meaningful inference and reliable parameter estimation. Experimentally collected response data lacking rich information may represent a bottleneck for inference. For example, binary response data provide a challenge for a model of hierarchical Bayesian belief updating such as the HGF, because the limited information contained in binary responses can prevent accurate inference on higher-level quantities of the model (Iglesias et al., 2021).

Here, we aim to test a potential solution to this problem – namely, a new response model which exploits binary information alongside continuous-valued response data. This approach provides a novel option to combine different data modalities in the HGF framework and model them in a joint fashion. The aim of the present analysis is to demonstrate the practical utility of this approach in application to empirical data.

3 RESEARCH HYPOTHESES / QUESTIONS

This project has the following central aims:

- 1) A quantitative comparison of response models that utilise binary and continuous-valued response data in different ways.
- 2) A quantitative assessment of whether and how parameters characterizing subject-specific learning behaviour are represented in an individual's measured response times.

4 DATA SET

To address the above highlighted questions, we will utilise the data collected as part of the SPIRL behavioural study. The data will be collected from right-handed healthy individuals, aged 18-40 years. The pilot data set consists of 20 participants, the main data contains behavioural data of 60 participants.

Each pilot and main study participant will complete a reward learning task, where participants are required to learn the probabilistic association between two cards and a monetary reward. Importantly, the underlying probabilistic associations in this experiment change over time (volatility). Participants are required to choose the card which they believe will be rewarded on a trial-wise basis which effectively corresponds to a (binary) prediction. Measured response times associated with these predictions will serve as the continuous data modality of interest.

Figure 1 | Reward probability trajectory (green line) for one of the two cards in the speed-incentivized reward learning task. Black dots represent outcomes on every single trial (1=reward, 0=no reward). Colour shadings indicate different phases throughout the experiment (blue=volatile, white=stable, grey=unpredictable).

The probabilistic trial structure is depicted in figure 1. The green trajectory indicates the reward probability of one of the two cards. The black dots indicate whether the respective card is rewarded on a given trial (1=reward, 0=no reward). As the reward probabilities of the two cards are complementary (summing to 1 at any given point during the experiment), the reward probability of the second card is simply the mirrored trajectory of the displayed trajectory. The different phases throughout the experiment are indicated by colour shading. Phases where volatility is high are shaded blue, phases during which the underlying probability structure remains stable are white. The phase from trial 75 to 95 is shaded in grey indicating that volatility is also high during this phase but in an unpredictable manner, as the underlying probability is 0.5 (both outcomes are equally likely).

Figure 2 | Experimental protocol of the speed-incentivized reward learning task.

Figure 2 depicts the detailed paradigm of the learning task. The stimulation consists of a fixation cross in the middle of the screen, the two cards that can be chosen, as well as a time bar. A trial – during which a prediction is made (duration 1700 ms) – is always followed by an inter-trial interval (ITI, timing is jittered). At the beginning of the next trial, the outcome of the previous trial is revealed (correct prediction: coin, incorrect prediction: crossed coin, no/missing prediction: “Keine Taste gedrückt!”). Simultaneously with the onset of a new trial, the time bar starts receding, signalling the available response time. The participant’s choice (predicted

card) is indicated by a grey frame and the filling level of the time bar indicates the relative amount of time required for prediction.

A customized payoff structure (for equations see Appendix A1) serves to incentivize fast responses while still emphasizing the importance of correct predictions (Heitz, 2014). Specifically, correct trials are rewarded, with the amount of the monetary reward depending on the speed of the response. Incorrect trials never yield a reward (independent of response speed). Block randomization across participants is used for the reward trajectories of the two cards as well as the card positions (left/right).

5 EXCLUSION OF DATA SETS

Data of all participants will be carefully checked for adequate quality. Data will be excluded from analysis if at least one of the following criteria is fulfilled:

- The task is not completed
- >10 NaN trials, encompassing ignored trials (no response & no feedback) and irregular trials with a $RT < 0.1s$
- Information from the debriefing does not match the participant's behaviour
- Evidence for problems with understanding the task instructions, resulting in poor performance as indicated by <65% correct predictions (where correctness is adjusted for the probabilistic structure of the task, as in (Iglesias et al., 2021), meaning that 122 correct predictions amount to an adjusted correctness of 100% in this task)
- Evidence for problems with fitting any of the behavioural models as determined by visual inspection of trajectories

6 COMPUTATIONAL MODELLING OF BEHAVIOURAL DATA

In this section, we provide a brief overview over the generative modelling framework used in this project.

6.1 Theory

6.1.1 The perceptual model

The Hierarchical Gaussian Filter (HGF) is a generative modelling framework for hierarchical Bayesian belief updating, describing the evolution of (hidden) states and how these give rise to sensory inputs that an agent receives. We will use a 3-level binary enhanced HGF (3b-eHGF) for the current application as introduced by (Mathys et al. *in prep.*), where the states evolve as Gaussian random walks (GRW) at all but the first level and the step-size of the GRW at any given level is determined by the next higher level (variance-coupling). The probability of the binary states at the lowest level originates from a simple sigmoid transformation of the quantity at the second level. Further details and equations of the generative model can be found in the Appendix (section A2) and in the publication by (Mathys et al., 2011).

6.1.2 The response model

The 3b-eHGF represents a concrete implementation of the "observing the observer" framework, where an observation or response model can be used to specify a mapping from inferred beliefs of an agent to observed responses as recorded during our experiment

(Daunizeau et al., 2010b, 2010a). We will augment our perceptual model (3b-eHGF) with a novel response model combining binary predictions and continuous-valued response times. The response model uses the perceptual model indirectly via its inversion (Mathys et al., 2014). The trial-by-trial update equations, representing the agent's variational inversion of the perceptual model using Variational Bayes (VB) under a mean-field approximation and a quadratic approximation to the variational energies can be found in (Mathys et al. *in prep.*) and in the Appendix (section A3).

As binary part of the response model, we use a unit-square sigmoid function mapping from the belief $\hat{\mu}_1^{(k)}$ at the lowest level of the 3b-eHGF that the next outcome will be 1 onto the probabilities $p(y_{bin}^{(k)} = 1)$ and $p(y_{bin}^{(k)} = 0)$ that the agent will choose response 1 or 0. For simplicity, we use $m^{(k)} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \hat{\mu}_1^{(k)}$ and we omit time indices on y and m :

$$p(y_{bin}|m, \zeta) = \left(\frac{m^\zeta}{m^\zeta + (1-m)^\zeta}\right)^y \left(\frac{(1-m)^\zeta}{m^\zeta + (1-m)^\zeta}\right)^{1-y}$$

The parameter ζ determines the steepness of the sigmoid function and is referred to as inverse decision temperature or inverse decision noise.

The continuous part of the response model consists of a linear mapping from beliefs to log-transformed reaction times (in ms). In the following, we provide a detailed overview over the different RT models in our model space.

6.2 Model Space

We define an initial set of combined response models that are all paired with a 3b-eHGF (perceptual model). The combination of binary predictions and continuous response times in these models is accomplished by summing the log-likelihood of two individual response models. In other words, we hereby make an independence assumption between the two streams of response data, which simplifies the combination of the streams. This assumption was made in absence of detailed knowledge regarding the precise nature of that relationship. However, for future applications, one can consider extending the current formulation by introducing weighting terms for the two different streams of response data.

For reasons of comparability, the binary part will be kept constant across all different response models, namely a unit-square sigmoid response model as introduced in section 6.1.2. For the continuous-part of the combined response models, we use a general linear model (GLM) to predict the log-transformed RTs on a trial-by-trial basis. The regressors of the different GLMs are quantities represented in the 3b-eHGF, e.g., an individual's estimated uncertainty about the outcome ($\hat{\sigma}_1^{(k)}$) at timepoint k . Equations describing the updates of the different quantities in the 3b-eHGF can be found in the Appendix (section A3). Our initial (hypothesis-driven) model space can be divided into 2 different families of models and includes the following GLM variants:

Informed response time family:

M1. Lawson-inspired logRT model (adapted from (Lawson et al., 2017))

$$\log(y_{rt}^{(k)}) \sim N\left(\beta_0 + \beta_1 S^{(k-1)} + \beta_2 \hat{\sigma}_1^{(k)} + \beta_3 \hat{\sigma}_2^{(k)} + \beta_4 e^{\hat{\mu}_3^{(k)}}, \Sigma\right)$$

$$\text{with } S^{(k-1)} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \begin{cases} -\log_2(\hat{\mu}_1^{(k-1)}) & \text{if } u^{(t)} = 1 \\ -\log_2(1 - \hat{\mu}_1^{(k-1)}) & \text{if } u^{(t)} = 0 \end{cases}$$

M2. Informational uncertainty and log-volatility model

$$\log(y_{rt}^{(k)}) \sim N(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \sigma_2^{(k)} + \beta_2 \hat{\mu}_3^{(k)}, \Sigma)$$

M3. Informational, environmental and outcome uncertainty model

$$\log(y_{rt}^{(k)}) \sim N(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \sigma_2^{(k)} + \beta_2 e^{(\kappa_2 \mu_3^{(k-1)} + \omega_2)} + \beta_3 \hat{\sigma}_1^{(k)}, \Sigma)$$

M4. Informational & environmental uncertainty model

$$\log(y_{rt}^{(k)}) \sim N(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \sigma_2^{(k)} + \beta_2 e^{(\kappa_2 \mu_3^{(k-1)} + \omega_2)}, \Sigma)$$

Uninformed response time family:

M5. Null model

$$\log(y_{rt}^{(k)}) \sim N(\beta_0, \Sigma)$$

M6. Linear decay model

$$\log(y_{rt}^{(k)}) \sim N(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \frac{k}{k_{max}}, \Sigma)$$

M7. Null model with 2 intercepts (correct/incorrect predictions)

$$\log(y_{rt}^{(k)}) \sim N(\beta_0^{(k)}, \Sigma)$$

$$\text{with } \beta_0^{(k)} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \begin{cases} \beta_{0,\text{correct}}^{(k)} & \text{if } y_{\text{binary}}^{(t-1)} = u^{(t-1)} \\ \beta_{0,\text{incorrect}}^{(k)} & \text{if } y_{\text{binary}}^{(t-1)} \neq u^{(t-1)} \end{cases}$$

A brief statement regarding the choice of models of the Informed response time family: The response time GLM of M1 was adapted from a model used in a previous study (Lawson et al., 2017) and tailored towards the mechanics of our task. Models M2-M4 are custom built response models, for which the motivation is mainly twofold. Firstly, the goal is to reduce the number of regressors entering the GLM and hence the complexity of the model compared to M1. Secondly, the idea is to include different types of uncertainty at different levels of the hierarchy described by our perceptual model, the 3b-eHGF. The HGF accommodates various forms of uncertainty, specifically, two sources of uncertainty, informational (“expected uncertainty”) and environmental (“unexpected uncertainty”), are clearly visible in the update equations of the 3b-eHGF. For a more detailed discussion regarding the different forms of uncertainty, please refer to (Mathys et al., 2014). In order to investigate the relevance of these estimates, the models M2-M4 were defined combining different forms of uncertainty.

6.3 Software

Behavioural data will be modelled using the *HGF Toolbox* as part of the open-source software package “Translational Algorithms for Psychiatry-Advancing Science (TAPAS, v5.0.0)” (Frässle et al., 2021). Additional open-source software packages used in this analysis are the VBA Toolbox (Daunizeau et al., 2014), RainCloudPlot library (Allen et al., 2021). All analysis scripts will be implemented in MATLAB version R2019b and analysis will be performed on the Euler cluster at ETH Zurich (for details, see <https://scicomp.ethz.ch/wiki/Euler>).

7 PREPROCESSING OF BEHAVIOURAL DATA

Preprocessing of the behavioural data involves the examination of measured response times (RT, $y_{rt}^{(k)}$) for implausible values. Trials with $y_{rt}^{(k)} < 0.1$ s indicate responses that are implausibly fast, suggesting that participants accidentally pressed the button or did not wait for the feedback from the previous trial (which also represents the start of the current trial). Therefore, we will classify these as irregular trials (missed response, however, filtering takes still place based on the input u) setting the values for predictions ($y_{bin}^{(k)}$) and RTs ($y_{rt}^{(k)}$) to NaN. Trials, in which participants failed to give a response before the maximal response time expired (1.7s) and therefore did not receive feedback about the correctness of a chosen card, are classified as ignored trials (filtering suspended for this trial). The input ($u^{(k)}$), binary ($y_{bin}^{(k)}$) and continuous ($y_{rt}^{(k)}$) response of the corresponding trial will be coded as NaN.

8 ANALYSIS OF PILOT DATA SET

For the analysis, recorded predictions (binary) and response times (continuous-valued) from the experimental paradigm (SPIRL task) were used. Descriptive analyses of the pilot data set ($n=20$) informed our decision about whether and how to proceed with the collection of data for the main study. Furthermore, the pilot data set served to define and refine a set of combined response models and to estimate prior distributions of model parameters for the analysis of the main study (held-out data set, see section 9.2.2).

8.1 Model-Agnostic Response Time Analysis

The measured response times from the pilot data set were subject to several descriptive analysis steps. The goal of these steps is to perform a set of basic sanity checks as well as a first qualitative assessment of differences in response times between different phases of our experimental paradigm. The descriptive analysis of the response times included visualizations of the individual log-transformed response time (logRT) trajectories as well as average logRT trajectories over all pilot participants. The distribution of logRTs in the pilot data set were visualized in a histogram. These are hypothesized to follow a normal distribution in log-space. A quantile-quantile (QQ) plot served as additional graphical tool for assessing normality. Furthermore, various boxplots will enable a more fine-grained analysis of logRTs. Specifically, logRTs were grouped and compared by phase (stable, volatile, unpredictable according to the colour shading in figure 1). In a separate boxplot, logRTs were grouped by blocks, where one block was defined as the number of subsequent trials with the same underlying probability. These figures provided a first qualitative assessment as to whether the experiment captured the hypothesized differences in RT across the different phases/blocks. Moreover, we will conduct a one-way ANOVA of average logRTs over subjects including the factor phase as a quantitative assessment of the effect of phase during the experiment on logRTs. If the ANOVA reveals a significant main effect of phase, post-hoc one-sample t-tests will be used to perform pairwise comparisons between the different levels (stable, volatile, unpredictable) of the factor phase.

8.2 Refinement of the Model Space

The pilot data set was used to assess the model space defined in section 6.2 in version 1 (date effective: 14.04.2021) of this analysis plan. Changes to the initial model space (as defined in v1) include:

- Addition of two models to the uninformed response time family:
 - The linear decay model was added to allow for a temporal drift in logRTs over the course of the experiment. This enables the linear decay model to account for systematic trends in the data. For instance, to explain an increase in response speed, e.g., due to familiarization with the task during the experiment or a slowing in response speed due to diminished attention or tiredness over the course of the experiment.
 - The null model with 2 intercepts represents a simple extension of the “standard” null model which has only one intercept. The 2 different intercepts allow to account for possible differences in average logRTs following correct and incorrect predictions, respectively. This is a simple alternative model to explain differences in response times based on inter-individual task performance and that is agnostic of quantities computed by the perceptual model such as outcome uncertainty, volatility, etc.
- Furthermore, we removed the delta model from the family of informed response time models. The regressors of the delta model encoded the trial-wise change in uncertainty and log-volatility estimates of the perceptual model. Fitting of the pilot data set revealed little evidence that the model provides a good explanation of the logRT data. Moreover, the delta model was the only model including the trial-wise change (i.e. difference between current and previous time-point) of quantities from the perceptual model, therefore making it conceptually different from all the other models considered. Therefore, we decided to exclude the model from our model space for the final analysis.

9 ANALYSIS OF MAIN EXPERIMENT

The analysis of the main experiment is divided into two parts: a model-agnostic and a model-based part. The model-agnostic data analysis includes separate analyses of the response time and the binary choice data. The steps of the model-based analysis encompass the specification of prior configurations for the main analysis based on the pilot data set, simulation analyses, testing of our research questions and posterior predictive checks. Note that this section has been added to the analysis plan as part of version 2 (date effective: 04.04.2022). Hereby, the parts of the analysis involving only the pilot data and/or synthetic data generated by our models have already been conducted (sections 9.2.2: *prior configurations*, section 9.2.3: *face validity of the model space*), which was necessary in order to be able to finalize our model space for hypothesis testing. To make the distinction clear, we use future tense throughout this section whenever we describe analyses that will be conducted only after publication of version 2 of this analysis plan. We use past tense when referring to analyses that have already been conducted prior to the publication of version 2.

9.1 Model-Agnostic Data Analysis

Because our research hypotheses are asking specific questions about the computational models we use (and therefore the model-based part of the analysis), the model-agnostic analysis of the collected behavioural data will serve mainly two purposes: (i) Performing sanity checks (e.g. regarding unwanted patterns of behaviour induced by our experimental paradigm, comparison of pilot and main data set), and (ii) assessing whether participants show certain expected effects of behaviour (e.g. differences in logRTs during different phases of the experiment).

9.1.1 Response time analysis

The analysis will include the same steps as the model-agnostic logRT analysis of the pilot data (see section 8.1).

9.1.2 Analysis of binary predictions

Model-agnostic analysis of binary response data will primarily be concerned with the assessment of expected behavioural patterns. Adjusted correctness of the participants' predictions (adjusted in the sense that we account for the probabilistic structure of our experiment) is calculated as part of the inclusion criteria for the analysis (see section 5 for more details). For both the pilot and the main data set, we will calculate participants' stay-probability after correct and incorrect predictions. This will serve as a primitive means to compare observed behaviour with simple heuristics (e.g. random responses). Resulting average values and standard deviation of stay-probabilities from the pilot and the main data set will be visualized.

9.2 Model-based Data Analysis

9.2.1 Model inversion

For the model-based analysis of the behavioural data, we invert generative models of behaviour using (Bayesian) inference as implemented in the *HGF Toolbox*. Maximum a posteriori estimates (MAP estimates) are computed as the minimum of the negative log joint using gradient-based optimisation techniques. By default, the HGF toolbox uses an optimisation algorithm from the quasi-newton methods family (Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno algorithm, BFGS). The variance of the posterior is obtained under a Laplace approximation to the negative log joint at the MAP. This allows for the specification of credible intervals on the obtained parameter estimates as well as the calculation of an approximate log model evidence (LME) as a measure of 'model goodness'.

For the present analyses, a multi-start optimisation approach is used to alleviate issues with the optimisation algorithm falling into local optima of the objective function. Specifically, 400 different starting points are used for the inversion of each subject and model. Of these 400 starting points, one always corresponds to the prior mean values of the different parameters (representing the default setting in the HGF toolbox), whereas the other 399 starting points are randomly sampled values from the respective prior distribution of the parameters.

As a pragmatic method to qualitatively assess the behaviour of the optimisation algorithm, values of the log joint as well as the free parameters will be visualised across iterations of the optimisation algorithm.

9.2.2 Prior configurations

In Bayesian inference, the specification of a model necessarily includes the specification of a range of *a priori* plausible values for every parameter across all the different models in our model space, i.e., the prior. The choice of priors can be driven by subjective factors, such as domain knowledge. Depending on the scientific context, this can pose problems (Daw, 2011). However, if specified in an appropriate and transparent manner, priors sensibly regularise our models and thus prevent overfitting. Here, to reduce the influence of subjective factors, we use a separate dataset in order to inform our priors. Additionally, as we believe in the importance of transparency about our choice of priors, we thoroughly document the specified priors for our analysis alongside an explanation of our choices.

For the specification of priors for the models in the present study, we made use of a held-out data set consisting of 20 pilot participants. Recently, similar approaches have been used for

comparable modelling endeavours (Harrison et al., 2021; Schöbi et al., 2021). Since all our priors take the form of a Gaussian, we estimated the sufficient statistics (mean and variance) of the prior densities that will be used in our main analysis via the following 2 step procedure:

1. Inversion of pilot data set ($N = 20$) using *initial prior* means and variances as listed in Table 1 for all models in our model space. These prior means and variances represent the default prior settings in the 3b-eHGF.
2. For every model m :
 - a. defining new prior mean pE_m as the robust mean estimate over MAP estimates obtained in step 1.
 - b. defining new prior variance pC_m as the robust variance estimate over MAP estimates obtained in step 1.

We will refer to this new set of priors, that we estimated via the above described procedure, as the *empirical priors* (as informed by the pilot data set). These empirical priors are listed in Table 2 and visualised in Figures 4 (main text) and A2-A7 (Appendix).

Remark: Due to the limited size of the pilot data set, robust mean and variance estimates were computed. For this, we used a variant of the minimum covariance determinant (MCD) method, namely the FAST-MCD algorithm developed by Rousseeuw and Van Driessen (Rousseeuw and Van Driessen, 1999).

Table 1 | Initial prior configurations. All parameters have Gaussian priors. Prior means are given in native space, prior variance in estimation (transformed) space.

Parameter	Prior mean (μ_{prior})	Prior variance (σ_{prior}^2)	Transformation
3-level binary eHGF			
$\mu_1^{(0)}$	NaN	NaN	none
$\mu_2^{(0)}$	0	0	none
$\mu_3^{(0)}$	1	0	none
$\sigma_1^{(0)}$	NaN	NaN	log
$\sigma_2^{(0)}$	0.1	0	log
$\sigma_3^{(0)}$	1	0	log
ρ_1	NaN	NaN	none
ρ_2	0	0	none
ρ_3	0	0	none
κ_1	1	0	log
κ_2	1	0	log
ω_1	NaN	NaN	none
ω_2	-3	4	none
ω_3	2	4	none
Unit-square Sigmoid			
ζ	48	1	log
logRT GLMs			

β_0	5.91	100	none
$\beta_{1,\dots,n}$	0	100	none
Σ	$\exp(-2)$	2	log

By adopting the procedure of estimating the priors of the model parameters using a held-out data set, we obtained individually tailored sufficient statistics of prior densities for each model. By construction, these values lay in the range of actual human behaviour for the present task while at the same time the subjectivity involved in the choice of priors is reduced to a minimum. However, we are aware of the fact that the *initial priors* used to fit the pilot data set in step 1 of our procedure influence the resulting estimates, albeit only in a limited fashion. Therefore, we provide a careful motivation, analysis and justification of our choice of *initial priors*.

Initial priors

We start with the priors on the perceptual model parameters (3b-eHGF) which are invariant across our model space. We chose to fix the value of all parameters except for the parameters ω_2 and ω_3 , describing the effect of tonic (time-invariant) volatility and meta-volatility, respectively, on the belief updates. We chose these two parameters as free parameters because they are of particular interest for concurrent theories of maladaptive behaviour in Computational Psychiatry as reflected by their frequent use in studies deploying the HGF (e.g. (De Berker et al., 2016; Lawson et al., 2021, 2017; Vossel et al., 2014)). Another reason for having only two free parameters is to avoid an overparametrized model. As described in Appendix F of (Mathys et al., 2014), this can be achieved by fixing the values of $\mu_i^{(0)}$ and κ_i , reflecting a choice of origin on the scale of x_i (where i indicates the level in the hierarchy of the HGF, here $i = 3$). The remaining parameters were fixed to values that either represent a neutral choice (e.g. $\mu_2^{(0)} = 0$ assuming no *a priori* bias towards either of the 2 outcome quantities) or logical choices ($\rho_2 = 0$ and $\rho_3 = 0$ as we have no particular reason to assume a drift in the evolution of the mean belief at any level). The choice of the initial values of the uncertainty about the belief on the second and the third level have little influence on the evolution of the belief trajectories in practice if set to appropriate values (Mathys et al., 2011), therefore we fixed them to the default values from the HGF Toolbox ($\sigma_2^{(0)} = 0.1$ and $\sigma_3^{(0)} = 1$).

We then tested whether the default priors on the parameters ω_2 and ω_3 are sensible choices. To this end, we tested whether these priors enable the model to cover a wide range of behaviour while at the same time not producing a large amount of “implausible” trajectories. This was ensured by qualitative analysis of the prior predictive densities of our models (van de Schoot et al., 2021). Figure 3 displays belief trajectories at the outcome level of the 3b-eHGF, generated by randomly sampling values of the free parameters of the perceptual model from their prior distributions.

Figure 3 | Belief trajectories at the outcome level of the 3b-eHGF ($\hat{\mu}_1$) resulting from 100 randomly sampled values of the free parameters ω_2 and ω_3 from their respective *initial prior* densities, are displayed. The sequence of binary inputs is visualized as sequence of green dots and the fine green line shows the underlying probabilistic structure of the task. Trajectories for different parameter values are displayed in blue, the thick black belief trajectory results from generation of synthetic data using the prior mean values of the free parameters.

An additional figure displaying results of a grid search performed on the two free parameters of the perceptual model can be found in Appendix section A4.1.

The choice of *initial priors* on the parameters of our combined observation models (unit-square sigmoid + logRT GLM variant) followed similar logic and reasoning as for the perceptual model. For the continuous part of the response models, the priors on the weights of the different logRT GLMs were chosen in a neutral fashion. The prior mean of the intercept (β_0) was set to the average logRT value of the entire pilot data set ($\bar{y}_{logRT} = 5.91$). The prior mean of all the remaining GLM weights (e.g. $\beta_{1,\dots,4}$ for M1, β_1 & β_2 for M2, etc.) was set to 0, i.e. no (direction of) effect was assumed a priori. A wide variance (100) ensured high degree of flexibility for the parameters to fit the logRT data of pilot subjects. The priors on the noise parameters in both parts of the combined response models (inverse decision noise parameter ζ , Gaussian response time noise parameter Σ) were chosen such that very little noise was assumed a priori. This choice was on one hand due to the lack of a better assumption (remember that the data-informed priors result from this step), on the other hand having the benefit of forcing the models to try to explain the data.

We would like to emphasize that the above-mentioned choice of *initial priors* can be debated and we are aware of the fact that alternative solutions exist. However, as illustrated by the qualitative analysis of prior predictive densities, our choices are reasonable for the current application. At the same time, we would like to remind the reader that the influence of the *initial priors* on conclusions about our research questions is reduced to a minimum as they only serve as the starting position to obtain *empirical priors* (as informed by the pilot data set) which are used in the main study. Moreover, as we do not perform any sort of model comparison at the current step, comparability (of *initial priors*) across models is not as important yet as it will become in later steps of the analysis. Hence, we now turn to the set of *empirical priors*, which were obtained from inversion of the pilot data set under the *initial priors*.

Empirical priors

Sufficient statistics of the *empirical priors* are listed in Table 2. Note that only the parameters whose priors are different from the initial values (Table 1) are listed. This is due to the fact that

only parameters with a non-zero initial prior variance (see column prior variance in Table 1) can vary and therefore be estimated from the pilot data. In the present analysis, these are the following parameters:

- the parameters ω_2 and ω_3 of the perceptual model describing the amount of tonic (time-invariant) volatility and meta-volatility, respectively, on the belief updates in the **3b-eHGF**
- the inverse decision noise parameter ζ of the binary part of the response model (**unit-square sigmoid**)
- all parameters of the different continuous parts of the response models (**logRT GLMs**) consisting of an intercept (β_0), the weights of the different regressors ($\beta_{1,\dots,n}$) and the Gaussian noise term (Σ)

Table 2 | Empirical priors. All parameters are estimated with Gaussian priors. Calculated empirical prior means (pE) and variances (pC) are both listed in estimation (transformed) space. Note that for every model only the free parameters are listed (for values of fixed parameters, see Table 1).

		Prc model		Obs model						
		3-level binary eHGF		Unit-square sigmoid	logRT GLM					
		ω_2	ω_3	$\log(\zeta)$	β_0	β_1	β_2	β_3	β_4	$\log(\Sigma)$
M1	pE_1	-1.24	0.20	0.45	5.41	0.01	1.66	0.03	0.06	-2.58
	pC_1	0.98	1.74	0.21	0.36	0.01	2.30	0.15	0.03	0.28
M2	pE_2	-1.23	0.25	0.59	6.06	-0.22	0.25			-2.62
	pC_2	1.02	2.44	0.23	0.74	0.48	0.06			0.26
M3	pE_3	-1.41	0.53	0.65	5.77	1.25	-0.28	0.27		-2.61
	pC_3	1.27	2.15	0.15	0.31	4.46	0.34	1.29		0.27
M4	pE_4	-1.23	0.31	0.56	6.06	-0.36	0.65			-2.53
	pC_4	0.91	1.90	0.25	0.66	0.42	0.81			0.27
M5	pE_5	-1.30	0.05	0.48	5.91					-2.33
	pC_5	0.92	0.35	0.25	0.08					0.30
M6	pE_6	-1.22	0.39	0.55	5.84	0.05				-2.52
	pC_6	1.14	0.53	0.71	0.07	0.08				0.39
M7	pE_7	-1.27	0.32	0.46	5.82	6.02				-2.47
	pC_7	1.00	0.53	0.24	0.06	0.12				0.26

Figure 4 displays the *initial priors*, the MAP estimates of the 20 pilot participants as well as the estimated *empirical priors* for every free parameter of M1 (3b-eHGF + Unit-square sigmoid + Lawson-inspired logRT model). The same visualisations for all the other models in our model space are shown in the Appendix (section A4.2, Figures A2-A7). From these figures, one can directly see that the informativeness of our priors increased from the *initial* to the *empirical priors* in a data-informed manner that avoids the direct problems of double-dipping (i.e. using the same data set to derive priors and to obtain posteriors)(van de Schoot et al., 2021). In other words, we have obtained a set of priors that are comparable across models as they are, by construction, optimized for each model to represent actual empirical data.

Figure 4 | *Initial priors* (dashed line), MAP estimates (black circles) resulting from model inversion on the pilot data set (n=20) and estimated *empirical priors* (solid black line) are displayed for all free parameters of M1 (3b-eHGF + Unit-square sigmoid + Lawson-inspired logRT model).

In order to get an intuition for the range of behaviour which is covered by our models under the respective *empirical priors*, we looked at the prior predictive densities. Figure 5 shows predicted belief trajectories ($\hat{\mu}_1$) at the lowest level of the perceptual model for all seven models in our model space. For the sake of completeness, prior predictive densities at all three levels of the perceptual model are shown in the Appendix in section A4.2 (Figures A8-A14) for each model in our model space.

Figure 5 | Belief trajectories at the lowest level of the 3b-eHGF ($\hat{\mu}_1$) for all seven models in our model space are displayed. Prior predictive densities were generated by randomly sampling 100 values of the free parameters from the respective *empirical prior* densities and plugging these values into the likelihood function of each model.

Predicted RT trajectories (under the *empirical prior* densities) are shown in Figure 6 for all models in our model space.

Figure 6 | (Pilot) prior predictive densities of the different logRT GLMs in our model space are displayed. Predicted logRT trajectories were generated by randomly sampling 100

values of the free parameters from the respective *empirical prior* densities and plugging these values into the likelihood function of each model.

The visualisations of the (*empirical*) prior predictive densities show that – by construction of the model space – all our models produce similar behaviour at the level of the perceptual model (Figures 5, A8-A14) but they differ considerably in the way they predict logRT data (Figure 6). This serves as qualitative sanity check of our estimation procedure used to determine priors from a held-out data set. The estimated *empirical priors* can now be used as basis for simulation analyses as well as the model-based analysis of the main data set.

9.2.3 Face Validity of the model space

To establish face validity of the models in our model space, we performed a set of recovery analyses following the guidelines outlined by Wilson and Collins (Wilson and Collins, 2019). Specifically, in a first step, we focused on the analysis of parameter recovery and model identifiability. In other words, we assessed whether in principle (i.e., knowing the “true” data-generating models and parameter values), we were able to identify the data-generating model as the model that explained the data best (model identifiability) and likewise for the parameter values of the data generating model (parameter recovery). In a second step, we tested whether data-generating model families could be recovered using the family-level comparison procedure which will also be used later to answer our primary research question.

Recovery analyses at the individual model level

In the first step of the individual model level recovery analyses, we drew 100 values for every free parameter of each model. Parameter values were sampled from their respective *empirical prior* distribution (see section 9.2.2 for a detailed description of prior evaluation and checking, and Table 2 for a list of the *empirical priors*). For each model, we then generated data from these 100 “synthetic subjects” by plugging the sampled parameter values into the likelihood function of the respective model (see Figures 5 and A8-A14 for the predicted trajectories of the perceptual models and Figure 6 for the noise-free predictions of the logRT GLMs). Note that the values of the noise parameters (inverse decision noise parameter ζ , Gaussian response time noise parameter Σ) used to generate synthetic binary responses and continuous response times are also sampled from the *empirical priors*. This means that the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the generated data (by design of the *empirical priors*) can be expected to lie in the same range as for empirical data. In the binary part of the response model, the parameter ζ determines the amount of inverse decision noise by characterizing the steepness of the sigmoid function, mapping from the belief at the outcome level of the 3b-eHGF ($\hat{\mu}_1^{(k)}$) to observed responses ($y_{bin}^{(k)}$). In the case of the continuous part of the response models, our models differ in their assumption about the amount of noise contained in the response time data ($y_{rt}^{(k)}$). This is a consequence of the design of our model space, where e.g., the null model assumes that the logRT data contain nothing but noise whereas models from the informed logRT family assume that the logRT data can be explained to a certain extent by quantities from the perceptual model (cf. noise-free predictions in Figure 6). Hence, the individually tailored *empirical* prior density of the Gaussian noise term Σ gives rise to SNRs that are specific for each individual model. Figure 7 shows simulated logRT trajectories for all seven models after the addition of noise.

Figure 7 | Simulated logRT trajectories (blue) for all seven models after the addition of noise to the logRT predictions. Black dashed lines represent upper and lower limits of logRTs as given by the constraints due to the design of the experiment ($\log(100)ms < \log(y_{rt}^{(k)}) < \log(1700)ms$).

In the next step, data simulated under one model was fitted by each of the models in our model space using the respective *empirical prior* configurations. Parameter recovery can be assessed by analysing the posterior parameter estimates of the “true” (data-generating) model. Specifically, simulated and estimated (i.e., recovered) parameter values were visualized in a scatterplot and Pearson correlation coefficients were computed to quantify recoverability. Adequate parameter recoverability was defined as significant correlation between simulated (true) and recovered parameter values as indicated by a p-value below 0.05. Model identifiability is quantified in two ways: the proportion of correctly identified models was calculated by using approximate LME scores of the different models. The results were visualized in a 7x7 confusion matrix (LME winner classification). To facilitate interpretation of the confusion matrix, balanced accuracy scores were computed by quantifying the mean proportion of correctly identified models for the whole model space. Analogously, a 7x7 confusion matrix containing the results from random-effects (RFX) Bayesian model selection (BMS) for every data generating model (for details regarding RFX BMS, see section 9.2.4 and (Rigoux et al., 2014; Stephan et al., 2009)) was computed. Adequate model recovery for the LME winner classification was defined as the proportion of correctly identified models exceeding the upper bound of the 90% confidence interval when assuming every model is equally likely a priori and for the RFX BMS as protected exceedance probabilities (XP) above 0.95.

Family-level recovery analysis

With this analysis, we aimed to verify that our chosen relative family comparison criterion (family-level RFX BMS) which will be used to test our primary research question (for details, see section 9.2.4) allows for faithful identification of the true (data-generating) families (Palmeri et al., 2017). Hence, we were mainly interested in quantifying the reliability with

which the family that is present in a given data set with a higher frequency is identified as the winning family by our Bayesian model comparison procedure.

We tested this using the following simulation procedure: Matrices containing approximate LME scores of 60 synthetic subjects (corresponding to the size of our main data set) were generated for different frequencies of the two model families ($f_{FamA} \in \{0, 0.1, 0.2, \dots, 0.9, 1\}$, where $1 = f_{FamA} + f_{famB}$). To obtain LME matrices that are as realistic as possible, we randomly drew approximate LME values of synthetic subjects obtained from the previously described model identifiability analysis. Next, we calculated the expected posterior family frequency (Ef) and the family exceedance probabilities (XP) using the implementation in the VBA Toolbox (for details on family-level RFX BMS and interpretation of the calculated metrics, please refer to section 9.2.4). For each condition (level of f_{FamA}), this procedure was repeated 5000 times to ensure robustness of our results. Individual as well as average Ef and XP values were plotted against true family frequencies. This allowed us to assess reliability of our hypothesis test and provides a basis for the interpretation of the results we will obtain from our hypothesis test (on the main data set).

9.2.4 Hypothesis testing

The main goal of this study is a quantitative comparison of response models that utilise binary and continuous-valued response data in different ways. More specifically, we want to know whether the family of informed response time models explains the collected data better than the uninformed response time model family or vice-versa. We will use a Bayesian test to quantify the evidence for the hypothesis that the response time data encodes computational quantities contained in the perceptual model. To this end, we test whether our set of informed response time models outperforms our set of uninformed response time models on the main data set. The exact hypothesis test that we will perform is random effects (RFX) family-level Bayesian model selection (BMS) as implemented in the VBA Toolbox. Family-level inference removes uncertainty about aspects of model structure other than the characteristic of interest (Penny et al., 2010). In the present study, we have no specific hypothesis about which of our candidate models explains the data best. Instead, we aim to show that informing our response time models using quantities from the perceptual model results in a better explanation of the data than using different variants of uninformed response time models. RFX BMS represents a hierarchical approach to model selection, treating the model as a random variable among subjects, allowing for inference on posterior family and model probabilities. RFX BMS accounts for group heterogeneity (different subjects may be using different winning models/families) and provides robustness against outliers as opposed to fixed-effects (FFX) procedures (Stephan et al., 2009).

For the family-level RFX BMS, we will use a uniform prior at the family level to avoid any unwanted bias in our inference. Given that this is related to the model level, the uniform family prior will be implemented by choosing the prior probability of model m as follows (Penny et al., 2010):

$$p(m) = \frac{1}{KN_k} \forall m \in f_k$$

where K is the number of families, f_k refers to the subset that contains all the models belonging to family k , and N_k refers to the number of models in the k th subset. This will be used for inference on the posterior family probabilities, which correspond to our posterior belief that family k generated the data. Additionally, we will compute family exceedance probabilities

(XP), which correspond to the belief that family k is more likely than any other of the K families, given the data from all subjects.

After acquiring data of 80 participants (including the pilot sample), hypothesis testing (family-level RFX BMS) will be conducted on the main data set ($N=60$) to test whether one of the two families of models exceeds an *a priori* defined level of evidence ($XP > 0.95$). Results (E_f , XP) from the family-level RFX BMS will be visualized in bar plots.

Secondary hypothesis testing

The secondary research question concerns a quantitative assessment of whether and how parameters characterising subject-specific learning behaviour are represented in an individual's measured response times. To this end, we first need to identify a single winning model – i.e. the model that best describes the measured data. Once this model has been identified, we can analyse the influence of the individual regressors of its response time GLM in a second step.

In order to identify the winning model, we will conduct a second RFX BMS analysis on the whole model space, this time on the level of individual models. In case a clear winning model can be identified (indicated by $PXP > 0.9$), we will examine posterior parameter estimates of the winning model to assess potential representations of subject-specific belief trajectories in an individual's measured response times. Specifically, MAP estimates resulting from subject-specific model inversion will be visualized for each of the free parameters of the winning model using raincloud plots. Furthermore, to quantify the importance of each free parameter, we will test its significance against the prior mean using one-sample t -test at a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$, Bonferroni-corrected for the number of performed tests (i.e. free parameters).

Remark: There is a simple reason why we opt for a second RFX BMS on the individual model level here instead of looking at the posterior model probabilities and PXP as computed during the family-level RFX BMS conducted to test our primary research question. As described above, we will implement a uniform family prior for the family-level RFX BMS which will lead to different prior probabilities at the individual model level due to the difference in size between our two families. As we are interested in examining the posterior parameter estimates of the model that explains the data best in this part of the analysis, a uniform prior at the model level is desirable as basis for the model selection procedure, hence the separate RFX BMS procedure on the individual model level.

9.2.5 Posterior Predictive Checking

Once we have inverted our models on the data set, we will engage in a number of posterior predictive checks. The idea behind posterior predictive checking is to examine the posterior distribution in order to assess whether the model provides sensible predictions. This will be done by simulating new data conditional on the obtained posterior distributions (van de Schoot et al., 2021). Specifically, we will use the Hessian of the negative log joint at the MAP estimate obtained during the optimisation to determine the posterior covariance matrix. This will allow us to construct an approximate multi-dimensional posterior for each model and subject. We will then sample 100 values from the calculated approximate posterior of each subject and model and use the sampled parameter values to generate synthetic response data (binary & continuous). The generated data will subsequently be compared to the empirical data. This comparison will be conducted at an individual subject level, as we also engage in subject-level inference in this project. In order to determine the quality of the posterior predictions of our

model, we specify the following criteria which we deem critical characteristics of the collected data set:

- binary predictions ($y_{bin}^{(k)}$): Adjusted correctness of binary responses will be calculated for each synthetic data set, generated from each subject-specific posterior for every model. Resulting values for both synthetic and empirical data of every subject are visualized via raincloud plots.
- continuous response times ($y_{rt}^{(k)}$): Plausibility of predicted response times will be assessed in a qualitative fashion by plotting the simulated RT trajectories generated from the posterior distribution from each subject alongside its empirical response time trajectory.

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APPENDIX

A1. Reward calculation in the speed-incentivized reward learning task

For every participant a performance index x_{perf} is calculated from measured response times of correct trials. Subsequently, the individual performance index x_{perf} is passed through a sigmoid function to calculate the reward R_{bonus} bounded between 0 CHF and 15 CHF. The coefficients of the sigmoid function were chosen such that the calculated reward R_{bonus} averages roughly 10 CHF. We based the choice of coefficients on behavioural data that was acquired as part of preliminary tests during the development of the learning task.

$$R_{bonus} = \frac{15}{1 + \exp(-0.13 * (x_{perf} - 36))}$$

$$\text{with } x_{perf} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n_{trials}} (t_{max} - t^{(k)}) * c^{(k)}}{n_{trials} * t_{max}} * 100$$

$$c^{(k)} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if prediction at trial } k \text{ correct} \\ 0 & \text{if prediction at trial } k \text{ incorrect} \end{cases}$$

where $t^{(k)}$ corresponds to the measured response time [s] at trial k , $t_{max} = 1.7$ is the maximum response time at any given trial and the total number of trials $n_{trials} = 160$.

A2. Generative model of the 3-level binary eHGF

$$p(x_3^{(k)} | x_3^{(k-1)}, \omega_3) = N(x_3^{(k)}; x_3^{(k-1)}, e^{\omega_3})$$

$$p(x_2^{(k)} | x_2^{(k-1)}, x_3^{(k)}) = N(x_2^{(k)}; x_2^{(k-1)}, e^{\kappa_2 x_3^{(k)} + \omega_2})$$

$$p(x_1^{(k)} | x_2^{(k)}) = s(x_2^{(k)})^{x_1^{(k)}} (1 - s(x_2^{(k)}))^{1-x_1^{(k)}}, \quad \text{with } s(x) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}$$

$$p(u^{(k)} | x_1^{(k)}) = (u^{(k)})^{x_1^{(k)}} (1 - u^{(k)})^{1-x_1^{(k)}}$$

where $u^{(k)}$ is the value of the binary input at timepoint k , $x_i^{(k)}$ are the hidden states and κ_2 , ω_2 and ω_3 are the parameters characterizing the evolution of states for an individual.

A3. Update equations from the approximate inversion of the 3-level binary eHGF

$$\mu_1^{(k)} = u^{(k)}$$

$$\mu_2^{(k)} = \hat{\mu}_2^{(k)} + \kappa_1 \sigma_2^{(k)} \delta_1^{(k)}, \quad \sigma_2^{(k)} = \frac{1}{1/\hat{\sigma}_2^{(k)} + \kappa_1^2 \hat{\sigma}_1^{(k)}}$$

$$\mu_3^{(k)} = \hat{\mu}_3^{(k)} + \sigma_3^{(k)} \frac{\kappa_2}{2} \hat{w}_2^{(k)} \hat{\delta}_2^{(k)}, \quad \pi_3^{(k)} = \hat{\pi}_3^{(k)} + \max\{0, \frac{\kappa_2^2}{2} w_2^{(k)} (w_2^{(k)} + r_2^{(k)} \delta_2^{(k)})\}$$

where for readability, the following definitions have been used:

$$\delta_1^{(k)} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mu_1^{(k)} - \hat{\mu}_1^{(k)}$$

$$\hat{\mu}_1^{(k)} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} s(\kappa_1 \hat{\mu}_2^{(k)})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{\sigma}_1^{(k)} &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \hat{\mu}_1^{(k)} \left(1 - \hat{\mu}_1^{(k)}\right) \\
\hat{\mu}_2^{(k)} &= \mu_2^{(k-1)} + t^{(k)} \rho_2 \\
\hat{\sigma}_2^{(k)} &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sigma_2^{(k-1)} + e^{(\kappa_2 \mu_3^{(k-1)} + \omega_2)} \\
\hat{\mu}_3^{(k)} &= \mu_3^{(k-1)} + t^{(k)} \rho_3 \\
\pi_3^{(k)} &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 1/\sigma_3^{(k)} \\
\hat{\pi}_3^{(k)} &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{\sigma_3^{(k-1)} + t^{(k)} e^{\omega_3}} \\
\hat{W}_2^{(k)} &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{t^{(k)} e^{(\kappa_2 \mu_3^{(k-1)} + \omega_2)}}{\sigma_2^{(k-1)} + e^{(\kappa_2 \mu_3^{(k-1)} + \omega_2)}} \\
W_2^{(k)} &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{t^{(k)} e^{(\kappa_2 \mu_3^{(k)} + \omega_2)}}{\sigma_2^{(k-1)} + t^{(k)} e^{(\kappa_2 \mu_3^{(k)} + \omega_2)}} \\
r_2^{(k)} &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{t^{(k)} e^{(\kappa_2 \mu_3^{(k)} + \omega_2)} - \sigma_2^{(k-1)}}{\sigma_2^{(k-1)} + t^{(k)} e^{(\kappa_2 \mu_3^{(k)} + \omega_2)}} \\
\hat{\delta}_2^{(k)} &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{\sigma_2^{(k)} + \left(\mu_2^{(k)} - \mu_2^{(k-1)}\right)^2}{\sigma_2^{(k-1)} + e^{(\kappa_2 \mu_3^{(k-1)} + \omega_2)}} - 1 \\
\delta_2^{(k)} &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{\sigma_2^{(k)} + \left(\mu_2^{(k)} - \mu_2^{(k-1)}\right)^2}{\sigma_2^{(k-1)} + t^{(k)} e^{(\kappa_2 \mu_3^{(k)} + \omega_2)}} - 1
\end{aligned}$$

In the above equations, parameters ρ_2 and ρ_3 implement a temporal drift and κ_1 represents the scaling of the coupling from the second level to the first. For our application, their influence has been removed by setting $\kappa_1 = 1$ and $\rho_2 = \rho_3 = 0$. The same holds for $t^{(k)}$, which is set to a value of 1 for any trial in the current application. The reason for explicitly listing these parameters in the update equations is to avoid confusions with the implementation of the update equations in the *HGF Toolbox*.

A4. Addendum: Analysis of prior distributions

A4.1 Grid search on free parameters under the initial priors

In order to make sure that the *initial priors* (for the sufficient statistics of the *initial prior* distributions see Table 1) range over values that produce sensible behaviour for our input trajectory, we examined the prior predictive density of the belief trajectory at the outcome level ($\hat{\mu}_1$) of the 3b-eHGF. Resulting belief trajectories from 100 randomly sampled values of the free parameters of the perceptual model are presented in the main text (Figure 3). In an additional step of the analysis of the *initial priors*, we performed a grid search for different values of the parameters ω_2 and ω_3 , where the covered grid of parameter values ranged from $\omega_{i,min} = \mu_{i,prior} - 3\sigma_{i,prior}$ to $\omega_{i,max} = \mu_{i,prior} + 3\sigma_{i,prior}$ with a step-size of 0.5 (where i indicates the level in the 3b-eHGF). This additional analysis allowed us to foster our understanding of

the connection between different parameter values and resulting belief trajectories at the outcome level of the 3b-eHGF. The results from this grid search are displayed in Figure A1.

Figure A1 | Belief trajectories at the outcome level of the 3b-eHGF ($\hat{\mu}_1$) resulting from a gridsearch varying the values of the free parameters ω_2 and ω_3 with a stepsize of 0.5 are displayed in the upper panel. Black dots in the upper panel are the binary inputs and the fine black line shows the underlying probabilistic structure of the experiment. Trajectories for different parameter values are colour coded according to the colour legend in the lower panel. The black cross in the lower panel indicates prior mean value of the free parameters and results in the thick black belief trajectory in the upper panel.

As already demonstrated in Figure 3, Figure A1 again clearly shows that a wide range of behaviour for our input trajectory is covered by the range of parameter values, from very slow belief updating to extremely fast learners. The prior mean of the parameter values corresponds to a behaviour that lays somewhere between the two extremes. One crucial observation is that for extremely high values of ω_3 (when combined with rather low values of ω_2) under our *initial prior*, the underlying model assumptions are violated (due to the posterior precision at the third level being evaluated as negative, which represents a violation of the quadratic approximation to the variational energies. For details, see (Mathys et al., 2014)). This explains the gap in the upper left corner of the colour legend in the lower panel of Figure A1. However, since this effect was only observed for rather extreme parameter values (under our *initial prior* densities), it can be expected that this will not pose any problems in practice. This conclusion is supported by the fact that the range of possible belief trajectories in the upper panel of Figure A1 shows that the parameter values for which our model can be evaluated cover a wide range of behaviour. This suggests that most of real human behaviour is likely to fall within that range of possible values. Lastly, it is important to keep in mind that, opposed to the belief trajectories in Figure 3, the set of belief trajectories displayed here in Figure A1 do not represent the mass of the *initial priors* but rather result from an equally spaced grid spanning roughly 99.7% of the prior distribution.

A4.2 Empirical priors

Probability density functions

Figures A2-A7 show the estimated *empirical priors* (as informed by the pilot data set) alongside the *initial priors* and the MAP estimates of the 20 pilot participants for models M2-M7 respectively. As shown and discussed for M1 (see Figure 4, main text), Figures A2-A7 analogously show that for all models in our model space, the informativeness of our priors increased from the *initial* to the *empirical priors* (data-informed manner, avoiding problems of double-dipping by using our held-out pilot data set).

Figure A2 | estimated *empirical priors* (solid black line) *initial priors* (dashed line) and MAP estimates (black circles) resulting from model inversion on the pilot data set (n=20) and are displayed for all free parameters of M2 (3b-eHGF + Unit-square sigmoid + Informational uncertainty and log-volatility model).

Figure A3 | estimated empirical priors (solid black line) initial priors (dashed line) and MAP estimates (black circles) resulting from model inversion on the pilot data set ($n=20$) and are displayed for all free parameters of M3 (3b-eHGF + Unit-square sigmoid + Informational, environmental, and outcome uncertainty model).

Figure A4 | estimated empirical priors (solid black line) initial priors (dashed line) and MAP estimates (black circles) resulting from model inversion on the pilot data set ($n=20$) and are displayed for all free parameters of M4 (3b-eHGF + Unit-square sigmoid + Informational & environmental uncertainty model).

Figure A5 | estimated empirical priors (solid black line) initial priors (dashed line) and MAP estimates (black circles) resulting from model inversion on the pilot data set ($n=20$) and are displayed for all free parameters of M5 (3b-eHGF + Unit-square sigmoid + Null model).

Figure A6 | estimated empirical priors (solid black line) initial priors (dashed line) and MAP estimates (black circles) resulting from model inversion on the pilot data set ($n=20$) and are displayed for all free parameters of M6 (3b-eHGF + Unit-square sigmoid + Linear decay model).

Figure A7 | estimated *empirical priors* (solid black line) *initial priors* (dashed line) and MAP estimates (black circles) resulting from model inversion on the pilot data set ($n=20$) and are displayed for all free parameters of M7 (3b-eHGF + Unit-square sigmoid + Null model with 2 intercepts).

Prior predictive densities

Prior predictive densities at all three levels of the perceptual model under the *empirical priors* for each of the seven models in our model space are displayed in Figures A8-A14. These visualisations are in line with our intuition, that all models in our model space produce comparable behaviour at the level of the perceptual model under the individually tailored *empirical priors*. Yet, the range of belief trajectories of the models slightly differs mainly due to the differences between the *empirical prior* distributions of the different models (for sufficient statistics of the respective distributions, see Table 2).

Figure A8 | Belief trajectories at all three levels of the 3b-eHGF ($\hat{\mu}_1$) for M1 (3b-eHGF + Unit-square sigmoid + Lawson-inspired logRT model) are displayed. Mean beliefs are presented on the left side whereas uncertainty estimates are depicted on the right. Prior predictive densities were generated by randomly sampling 100 values of the free parameters from the respective *empirical prior* densities and plugging these values into the likelihood function.

Figure A9 | Belief trajectories at all three levels of the 3b-eHGF ($\hat{\mu}_1$) for M2 (3b-eHGF + Unit-square sigmoid + Informational uncertainty and log-volatility model) are displayed. Mean beliefs are presented on the left side whereas uncertainty estimates are depicted on the right. Prior predictive densities were generated by randomly sampling 100 values of the free parameters from the respective *empirical prior* densities and plugging these values into the likelihood function.

Figure A10 | Belief trajectories at all three levels of the 3b-eHGF ($\hat{\mu}_1$) for M3 (3b-eHGF + Unit-square sigmoid + Informational, environmental, and outcome uncertainty model) are displayed. Mean beliefs are presented on the left side whereas uncertainty estimates are depicted on the right. Prior predictive densities were generated by randomly sampling 100 values of the free parameters from the respective *empirical prior* densities and plugging these values into the likelihood function.

Figure A11 | Belief trajectories at all three levels of the 3b-eHGF ($\hat{\mu}_1$) for M4 (3b-eHGF + Unit-square sigmoid + Informational & environmental uncertainty model) are displayed. Mean beliefs are presented on the left side whereas uncertainty estimates are depicted on the right. Prior predictive densities were generated by randomly sampling 100 values of the free parameters from the respective *empirical prior* densities and plugging these values into the likelihood function.

Figure A12 | Belief trajectories at all three levels of the 3b-eHGF ($\hat{\mu}_1$) for M5 (3b-eHGF + Unit-square sigmoid + Null model) are displayed. Mean beliefs are presented on the left side whereas uncertainty estimates are depicted on the right. Prior predictive densities were generated by randomly sampling 100 values of the free parameters from the respective *empirical prior* densities and plugging these values into the likelihood function.

Figure A13 | Belief trajectories at all three levels of the 3b-eHGF ($\hat{\mu}_1$) for M6 (3b-eHGF + Unit-square sigmoid + Linear decay model) are displayed. Mean beliefs are presented on the left side whereas uncertainty estimates are depicted on the right. Prior predictive densities were generated by randomly sampling 100 values of the free parameters from the respective *empirical prior* densities and plugging these values into the likelihood function.

Figure A14 | Belief trajectories at all three levels of the 3b-eHGF ($\hat{\mu}_1$) for M7 (3b-eHGF + Unit-square sigmoid + Null model with 2 intercepts) are displayed. Mean beliefs are presented on the left side whereas uncertainty estimates are depicted on the right. Prior predictive densities were generated by randomly sampling 100 values of the free parameters from the respective *empirical prior* densities and plugging these values into the likelihood function.

REVISIONS

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Version 1	Date: 14.04.2021	Date effective: 14.04.2021

Revision:	Date effective:	Description of change:
Version 2	04.04.2022	<p>Changes to version 1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • updated foreword • updated size of main data set • updated figure 2 (task protocol) • updated exclusion criteria for analysis (section 5): removed test for goodness of fit, added adjusted correctness of binary predictions as criterion • prc model: replaced 3-level binary HGF with 3-level binary <u>enhanced</u> HGF (3b-eHGF) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ mentioning in the main text & references ○ Appendix A3 (update equations) • refined model space (added linear decay model and null model with 2 intercepts, removed delta model) and extended information on motivation and assumptions underlying the combined response models • explicit formulation of 2 model families (informed & uninformed response time families) • updated list of software libraries (incl. references), MATLAB version and Euler cluster used for the analysis • added one-way ANOVA + post-hoc one-sample t-tests for model-agnostic response time analysis of pilot data set (section 8.1) • changed tense from future to past in section 8 (analysis of pilot data set), as this has already been conducted upon publication of v2 of this analysis plan • correction of typos throughout sections 1 - 8.1 <p>New chapters added as part of version 2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8.2 Refinement of the model space • 9 Analysis of main experiment • Appendix A4: Addendum: Analysis of prior distributions